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SELECTED FEATURES OF FILM TRANSLATION AS THE KEY ISSUE IN ACQUIRING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the basic key points of film translation as a core issue in language acquiring. Within the given project work, every detail of the film translation is clearly explained and outlined the process. The project work illustrates the table with the information gained from the experience among the tenth grade students. Particularly, the paper consists the analyze of the students' translation versions from the English film extracts.

Keywords: film translation, localization, dubbing, translation with subtitles, word for word translation, equivalent translation, paraphrasing of the idioms, calque, cultural difficulties, slang usage.

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INGLIZ TILINI CHET TILI SIFATIDA EGALLASHNING ASOSIY MASALASI SIFATIDA FILM TARJIMASINING TANLANGAN XUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola filmlarni tarjima qilishning asosiy nuqtalarini tilni o'zlashtirishda asosiy muammo sifatida ko'rib chiqadi. Ushbu loyiha ishining bir qismi sifatida filmlarni tarjima qilishning har bir tafsiloti batafsil tushuntiriladi va jarayon tavsiflanadi. Loyiha ishining illyustratsiyasi sifatida o'ninchi sinf o'quvchilari bilan ishlash tajribasidan olingan ma'lumotlar ko'rsatilgan jadval keltirilgan. Xususan, maqolada ingliz tilidagi film parchalaridan talabalarning tarjima qilingan versiyalari tahlili keltirilgan

Kalit so'zlar: film tarjimasini, lokalizatsiya, dublyaj, subtitrlar bilan tarjima, so'zma so'z tarjima, ekvivalent tarjima, iboralar izohi, kalka tarjimasini, jargon.

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ИЗБРАННЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА ФИЛЬМОВ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОГО ФАКТОРА В ОВЛАДЕНИИ АНГЛИЙСКИМ ЯЗЫКОМ КАК ИНОСТРАННЫМ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье рассматриваются основные моменты перевода фильмов как ключевой проблемы в овладении языком. В рамках данной проектной работы подробно объясняется каждая деталь перевода фильмов и описывается процесс. В качестве иллюстрации к проектной работе приведена таблица с информацией, полученной из опыта работы с учащимися десятого класса. В частности, статья содержит анализ переводных версий студентов из отрывков фильмов на английском языке.

Ключевые слова: перевод фильма, локализация, дублирование, перевод с субтитрами, дословный перевод, эквивалентный перевод, перефразирование идиом, калькирование, культурные трудности, употребление сленга

INTRODUCTION.

Currently intensively developing world requires everyone to be in one tune with it. Being as an international language, acquiring English is one of the most demanding tasks people are to fulfill. In this sense, many studies are being and have been carried out to opt better way to obtain the language. In particular, watching English movies whether with translation or without, could be one of the most effective techniques.

This article suggests some notions of how the film translation might serve as the core issue in learning English and contains the analyzed data on the project work conducted with 10th grade students for researching those phenomena profoundly.

First of all, let's see what the film translation itself means and its advantage in language acquisition. As the writer Edith Grossman wrote in her book, "Translation expands our ability to explore through literature the thoughts and feelings of people from another society or another time. It permits us to savor the transformation of the foreign into the familiar and for a brief time to live outside our own skins, our own preconceptions and misconceptions. It expands and deepens our world, our consciousness, in countless, indescribable ways."

MATERIAL AND METHODS.

On this basis, many scholars have contributed on the translation studies, such as Mona Baker, Susan Bassnett, John Dryden and others. According to these scientists, materials can be translated with different strategies like word for word translation as John Dryden suggests, or equivalent translation as Mona Baker states. Any kind of translation can be effective in English language learning. Recent surveys indicate, that in academics the lessons cannot be conducted without using translation, as it is nearer way to achieve the target goal. However, current linguists prefer not to use translation in acquiring the language, since it is an old traditional technique. Despite these opposing views, there are some cases that the translation should be included for gaining better understanding. In these terms, usage of film translation in language learning might be considered to be one of the most effective concepts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.

It is very important to choose a movie that is suitable for the age and interests of language learners. It makes no sense when the non-native speakers are not interested in the movie which is going on during the learning process and they do not want to work on the translation. Secondly, the chosen movie must be rich in phrases and idioms, so that the learners can learn them from translating into their own language. Further passage represents the process of film translation and its features.

How are the films translated and the role of the translator in the process?

The localization is not the process that is translated word by word or it is not merely a dubbing, but it is a matching the film to the condition of the country into which language is being translated. This is far more difficult and serious process than to localize the video. This complex

process is fulfilled by the specialized companies. As, this work demands its executors a great experience and real professionalism. The film translation is a field of work that contains some work steps of specialists doing their job turn by turn. The process is not by the directors, but by the producers.

It is not the translator who begins the process of the film translation. Before the needed material reaches to the translator, it passes several stages. At first, the distributors confirm the localizing version. Then according to this confirmed decision businessmen start their part of work. They begin to prepare advertisement materials. After that the resources for localization are produced in the studio. The next step is an arrangement of dialogue scripts and time codes (the time determining the beginning and the end of each actor's speech) into the edit paper. (Sometimes the time codes are put by the translators themselves). After all the small extracts of the whole film are provided to the translator.

The localization of the film and the typical features of working with it.

The decision about the localization format is made by the distributors and producers. The translator performs his part of the duty. At last, how the film is presented to the viewers depends on the type of the translation.

Translation with subtitles

This type of translation is getting more popular than others. If the film is not dubbed, but given with subtitles, the viewer will have a chance to hear the original voice of the actors and the typical features of the pronunciation. For example, the timbre of the actors and so on. Moreover, this translation does not need much experienced working as in other localizing processes. To organize the subtitles is even easier job. Except the right translation of the oral speech, the main thing that is required from the translator is to match the phrase.

Difficulties of the translator in the film translation.

It is quite a necessary skill for the translator to be aware of every nuance of phrases, set expressions, idioms or jokes in target language, as it is the key feature to the high quality film presentation to the audience. Another task of the translator is to interpret the special moments of the film so precisely that the audience could comprehend every single phrase or expression as the screenwriter and film director intended to do. This process is typically complex with its cultural aspects and slang usage in speech. The translator should take into consideration the gap between the cultures of two nations, their barriers, limits and taboos in speech. For instance, the American films especially vary from the other eastern nations film with their free use of slang, jargons or taboos. Due to this reason, it is the translator's duty to determine what to translate or what to remain as an original version.

As many linguists worked on the field of translation, its types and techniques the translators should be able to choose an appropriate translation type for better understanding of the text. For example, equivalent, borrowing translations and calques can be suitable for translating idioms or phrases. Another option could be the suggestion of Chesterman to paraphrase the idiom if there is no version in the target language. Other linguists, such as Baker (1992-2011:42-43), Dimitriy (2002-17:), Toury (1995:82) claim that the idioms can be even omitted wholly if the translator couldn't find the right equivalent of it.

For analyzing the phenomena on the film translation, I carried out a project with the tenth grade students. Further below it is given a description of the project work, its curriculum and process.

The project work based on the show of the movie can be divided into several parts or several stages. As, the expected result may not be reached just in one step. Here is given a table of the suggested project plan that can be fulfilled by a researcher.

Table I

Stages	Procedure	Researcher's task	Learners' task
1	Overviewing of the film translation based lesson	Explaining the lesson steps, how the film is translated in mother tongue	Understanding the film translation process

2	Film extract with subtitles (animation: Madagascar 1)	Preparing the movie extract with subtitles, presenting the film in the lesson	Watching the movie with subtitles
3	Film extract with subtitles (fantasy: Captain America)	Showing the movie extracts with subtitles, telling students to translate the jokes, idioms or fixed phrases using dictionary	Watching the movie with subtitles, translating the jokes, idioms and phrases using dictionary
4	Film extracts with translations (animation: Madagascar 1), (fantasy: Captain America)	Showing the movies with translations, comparing the professional translations with the translations of the learners	Analyzing the versions of the professionally translated phrases with their own versions

These are only suggested film extracts. The research conductor can choose any movies he/she prefers. But it is preferable to opt a movie that contains many phrases used in language for analyzing more speech. What is more, the learners will have an opportunity to compare these phrases in their own language

Movies	English version	Learners	Translation of the Learners	Original translation
Madagascar1 Extract 1	Martin: -Don't talk with your mouth. What the heck is this doing in this?	Learner 1 Bakhtiyarov Rajabbay	-Gapirmay tur hozir. To'xta, bu nima?	Martin: -Og'zingni ochmay tur, xo'pmi? Ha topdim, bu og'zingga qanday tushib qoldi?
		Learner 2 Rakhimov Inoyat	-He говори таким ртом. Вот оно что, что это делает там?	
		Learner 3 Matkarimov Fakhriddin	-Ko'p gapirma. Nima bo'lyapti?	
Madagascar1 Extract 2	Martin: -Thanks man, you're putting it behind the tooth, you all right. Alex: -These aren't even on the shelf yet here. Look!	Learner 1 Bakhtiyarov Rajabbay	Martin: -Oooh, katta rahmat do'stim. Sen sovg'ani tishing tagida qo'yganmiding? Alex: -Hali bular sotuvda ham mavjud emas, qara, qara!	Martin: -Ooo rahmat, tishlaring orasiga yashirganmiding-a?! Obbo qiziqchi ey! Alex: -Buni qara, bu hali sotuvda yo'q, qara!
		Learner 2 Rakhimov Inoyat	Martin: -Ooo, спасибо друг. Ты это между зубами держал? Alex: -Это ещё и в продаже нет здесь. Смотри!	
		Learner 3 Matkarimov Fakhriddin	Martin: -Rahmat, sen buni tishing orasida saqlagansan, to'g'rimi? Alex: -Hammasi yaxshi, bu hali javonga ham qo'yilmagan. Qara!	
	Martin: -...in fact I'll be here for my whole life, 365	Learner 1 Bakhtiyarov Rajabbay	Martin: -Bu hafta men bu yerda bo'laman, to'g'rirog'i men bu yerda bir yil	Martin: - Men bu yerda 1 hafta bo'laman, ya'ni qochib ketgunimcha, 365

Madagascar1 Extract 3	days a year including Christmas, Hanukkah, Halloween, Kwanza		bo'laman va bu yil o'z ichiga 365 kun va barcha Amerika milliy bayramlarini oladi	kunu 1 yil
		Learner 2 Rakhimov Inoyat	Martin: - В целом я буду здесь всю мою жизнь, 365 дней в году включая Навруз, Хайит и Новый год.	
		Learner 3 Matkarimov Fakhriddin	Martin: -Men butun hafta, to'g'rirog'I shu yerda butun hayotimni, bir yilda 365 kun, yana Yangi yil, Hannuka, Yangi yil, Xellovin bayramlarida ham shu yerda bo'laman.	

As can be seen in the table, the learners translated the phrases differently. If one of them translated the phrase word for word, another one gave the equivalent of it. The other one translated the given phrase adding an extra word to emphasize the meaning.

CONCLUSIONS.

Summarizing all, acquiring language is a multi-faceted process. The learners have an opportunity to obtain the target language in various ways. Film translation could be the one that of a great assistance in this process. However, some difficulties and problems in translating the language may occur, so the translator ought to be aware of every detail in cultural aspects of both languages. Film translation offers a rich and dynamic platform for acquiring English as a foreign language, with its unique features serving as both challenges and opportunities for language learners. Through the lens of film translation, learners can engage with authentic language use, cultural nuances, and diverse linguistic expressions. Through selected features such as subtitles, dubbing and voice-over, learners navigate language barriers while immersing themselves in the rich tapestry of English-language cinema. However, the effectiveness of film translation hinges on careful consideration of linguistic accuracy, cultural sensitivity, and pedagogical relevance. As educators and learners embrace the dynamic interplay between film and language acquisition, they unlock new avenues for linguistic proficiency and intercultural understanding in the global landscape.

References / Iqtiboslar / Сноски

[1] Arcario, P. [1993]. Criteria for selecting video materials. In Video in second language teaching: Using, selecting, and producing video for the classroom, ed. S. Stempleski and P. Arcario [pp. 109-122]. Alexandria, VA: TESOL Inc.

[2] Ayand, F. K., & Shafiee, S. [2016]. Effects of English and Persian Subtitles on Oral Fluency and Accuracy of Intermediate Iranian EFL Learners. International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature, 5[3], 133-144.

[3] Bashir, M., Azeem, M., & Doger, A.H. [2011]. Factor effecting students, English speaking skill. British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences, 2[1], 34-5

[4] Brown, J. D. [2005]. Testing in language programs. New York: McGraw-Hill.

[5] Cohen, J. [1988]. Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences [2nd ed.]. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.

[6] Danan, M. [2004]. Captioning and Subtitling: Undervalued Language Learning Strategies. Meta, 49 [1], 67-73.

- [7] Davies, P., & Pears, E. [2000]. *Success in English Teaching*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [8] De Bot, K., Jagt, J., Janssen, H., Kessels, E., & Schils, E. [1986]. Foreign television and language maintenance. *Interlanguage studies bulletin* [Utrecht], 2[1], 72-82.
- [9] Ellis, R. [2008]. *The study of second language acquisition*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [10] Efrizal, D. [2012]. Improving student's speaking through communicative language teaching method at Mtsja-alhaq, sentot Ali Basa Islamic boarding school of Bengkulu, Indonesia, *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2[20], 127-134.
- [11] Fahim, M., & Vaezi, R [2011]. Investigating the effect of visually-enhanced input on the acquisition of lexical collocations by Iranian intermediate EFL learners: A case of verb-noun lexical collocations. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 2[3], 552-560.
- [12] Harmer, J. [2007]. *How to teach English*. London: Pearson Longman.
- [13] Hayati, A., & Mohmedi, F. [2011]. The Effect of Films with and Without Subtitles on Listening Comprehension of EFL Learners. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 42[1], 181-192.
- [14] Ishihara, N., & Cohen, A. D. [2010]. *Teaching and learning Pragmatics: Where language and culture meet*.
- [15] Harlow, UK: Pearson. Jindathai, S. [2015]. Factors affecting English speaking problems among engineering students at Thai-Nichi institute of technology. In *Selected Proceedings of the 3rd National Interdisciplinary Academic Conference, ThaiNichi Institute of Technology* [pp. 344-8].

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